

Correlation Analysis of Reactivity in the Oxidation of 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diaryl-4-piperidones by Peroxomonosulphate

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Kinetics of oxidation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-(diphenyl/di-*p*-tolyl/di-*p*-anisyl/di-*p*-chlorophenyl/di-*p*-nitrophenyl)-4-piperidones by peroxomonosulphate in aqueous acetic acid medium have been studied. The reactions are first order, both in the piperidone and in the oxidant. Electron-withdrawing groups are found to accelerate the rate of oxidation and the electron-releasing groups retard it. The Hammett $\rho\sigma$ relationship is used to correlate reactivity with structure. The rates of oxidation show an excellent correlation with σ^+ values with a positive reaction constant ρ . A linear isokinetic relationship substantiates the validity of linear free energy relationships. Correlation analysis effectively supports the proposed mechanism.

Though a number of publications have appeared on the rate of oxidation of 4-piperidones by various oxidants¹, structure-reactivity correlation studies which are effective tools in deducing the reaction mechanism are limited. Literature survey reveals that no report has so far appeared on the kinetics of oxidation of 4-piperidones by peroxomonosulphate (PMS). In order to understand the participation of phenyl ring during oxidation and also to expand the scope of correlation studies in this field the present work was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The main product of oxidation is the corresponding α -ketol. The overall reaction can be represented as equation (1).

PMS undergoes a two-electron change. This accords with the stoichiometry 1 : 1. The reaction follows a second order kinetics, first order each in [PMS] and [Piperidone] (Table 1).

TABLE-1 EFFECT OF VARYING [PMS] AND [PIPERIDONE] ON THE RATES OF OXIDATION

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	3,5-diMe (<i>p</i> -H) 323 K	Piperidones			
		<i>p</i> -CH ₃ 323 K	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ 323 K	<i>p</i> -Cl 308 K	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ 308 K
× 10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)					
[PMS] × 10 ³					
1.0	3.06	2.11	2.57	3.77	17.88
1.5	3.12	2.13	2.57	3.79	17.86
2.0	3.06	2.22	2.56	3.87	17.89
2.5	3.04	2.23	2.57	3.85	17.85
[Piperidone] × 10 ²					
1.75	2.68	1.88	2.23	3.28	15.65
2.00	3.06	2.11	2.57	3.77	17.88
2.25	3.44	2.37	2.89	4.25	20.12
2.50	3.80	2.64	3.18	—	—

This leads to the following mechanism (equations 2 and 3) and rate law (4).

The excellent linear plots of k_1 versus [Piperidone] passing through the origin, rules out the absence of any stable complex formation and self-decomposition of PMS². Thermodynamic parameters and activation parameters were evaluated from the values of k_2 at different temperatures. The entropy and enthalpy

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = k k_2 k_3^{-1} [\text{PMS}] [\text{Piperidone}] \quad (4)$$

of activation of the oxidation of the five piperidones are linearly related ($\gamma = 0.998$) and the value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the slope of this plot is 383.9 K. The validity of the isokinetic relationship was checked using Exner's plot. A linear isokinetic relationship conforms to the validity of linear free energy relationships³ in the present investigation.

Hammitt plot : In the present study, it has been observed that electron-withdrawing substituents in the phenyl ring increase the rate while electron-releasing substituents decrease the rate as compared to 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidone in which the phenyl ring is unsubstituted. The observed reactivity order is $p\text{-NO}_2$ ($k_2 = 8.94 \times 10^{-2}$) > $p\text{-Cl}$ ($k_2 = 1.88 \times 10^{-2}$) > $p\text{-H}$ ($k_2 = 0.39 \times 10^{-2}$) > $p\text{-OCH}_3$ ($k_2 = 0.30 \times 10^{-2}$) > $p\text{-CH}_3$ ($k_2 = 0.25 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

The rate constants when plotted against substituent constant σ (Fig 1; $\gamma = 0.97$) do not yield a good correlation. For the 'insulated' reaction series the constants, σ° have been applied extensively to obtain better correlation⁴. In the piperidones investigated as there is intercalation of methyne group between the reaction site and the ring carrying substituent, we have attempted to correlate the rate constants with σ° values (Fig 1; $\gamma = 0.99$). So we observe that the rate constants give

Fig. 1. Hammett plot.

a better correlation with σ° rather than σ values. It is noteworthy that a correlation between rate constants and σ° values has been made for the first time in this field.

As the reaction site is only one atom away from the ring carrying substituent, the reaction constant ρ value is high, thereby indicating the high susceptibility of the reaction to polar effects. In the formation of transition state in the rate-limiting step there is an increase in electron density on the α -carbon atom which is facilitated by electron-withdrawing groups at the *para*-position of the phenyl ring and hence positive ρ value is observed ($\rho = 1.61$ at 308 K).

Correlation analysis made in the present investigation thus effectively supports the proposed mechanism.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Potassium peroxomonosulphate under the trade name 'oxone' (du Pont)⁵ was a triple salt with the composition $2\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot \text{KHSO}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$. The concentra-

tion of peroxomonosulphate solution was estimated iodometrically. The preparation procedure of piperidones was the same as reported in literature⁶. Piperidone solution was always prepared fresh.

Experiments were carried out in aqueous 75% (v/v) acetic acid under pseudo-first order conditions with ten-fold excess of piperidone at a constant ionic strength (0.05 M) maintained by the addition of sodium acetate and at a desired temperature. The kinetics of the reaction was followed by monitoring the disappearance of peroxomonosulphate by iodometry for at least 50% utilisation of the oxidant and the results were found to be reproducible within $\pm 2\%$ error.

Stoichiometry was established by estimating unchanged peroxomonosulphate by iodometry. Product analysis was carried out under the condition [PMS] \gg [Piperidone] and the main product was identified by tlc and nmr and ir spectral studies.

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